

Potentiometric Study of the System Mandelic Acid-Acid Dichromate in Presence of Manganous Ions

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The oxidation of mandelic acid by acid dichromate in presence and absence of Mn^{2+} has been potentiometrically studied at room temperature under a wide range of conditions (H_2SO_4 varying from 14*N* to 4*N* and the Mn^{2+} , from nil to saturated). The results are comparable with those reported earlier for lactic acid¹. Pure benzoic acid is formed in 14*N*-10*N* H_2SO_4 , but addition of Mn^{2+} suppresses this reaction and when enough Mn is present, pure benzoylformic acid is formed. Mn^{2+} ions always increase the rate of oxidation to benzoylformic acid.

We have reported earlier the results of oxidation of lactic acid¹. The present communication is an extension of the work to a similar aromatic acid, mandelic acid, which may be oxidised as:

Reactions (1) and (3) have been reported by Rodd². These oxidations take place in presence of dilute nitric acid or acid permanganate. On the other hand, when the oxidising agent is lead tetra-acetate, one obtains benzaldehyde (reaction 2)³. When one starts with the ester and the oxidising agents are lead tetra-acetate or selenium dioxide, the product reported is phenylglyoxalic ester^{3,4}. Waters *et al.*⁵ used V(v) in 0.5-5*N* perchloric acid and obtained a quick oxidation in accordance with reaction (2), followed by a slow oxidation under (3). The same results were obtained with manganic pyrophosphate in 4*N*- H_2SO_4 . Krishna and Tiwari⁶ also reported a reaction in accordance with (2) in presence of Ce (iv) and 0.5-2*N* H_2SO_4 . West and Skoog⁷ also used V (v), but in H_2SO_4 of concentration above 4*N*, and found results shown in reaction(3)⁷.

It will be seen that the hydroxyl in the α -position may be oxidised either to the aldehydic group or the ketonic group. Lead tetra-acetate, V(v), SeO_2 , and $Mn_2(P_2O_7)_3$ lead to reaction (2), whereas dilute nitric acid and acid permanganate lead to reaction (1). Since

1. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 765.

2. "Chemistry of Carbon Compounds", p. 903.

3. Baeyer and Kates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1482, 1484.

4. Aston *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 901.

5. *Ibid.*, 1955, 217, 1961, 630.

6. *Ibid.*, 1961, 3097.

7. *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 583.

we have already noted the analogue of reaction (1) in lactic acid-dichromate mixture earlier, we have extended our investigation in order to ascertain how far the same results are encountered with the aromatic acid chosen and how far the results are modified by the presence of Mn^{2+} .

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure adopted was similar to that described previously⁸. Preliminary experiments showed that these potentiometric titrations were smooth only when the $K_2Cr_2O_7$ - H_2SO_4 mixture was in the cell. In the reverse titration, a drift in potentiometric readings over 2 to 3 hours was observed.

Accordingly, in all these experiments we started with 50ml of 0.005M $K_2Cr_2O_7$, made to the desired concentration of H_2SO_4 . This was equivalent to 0.25 ml of M/1- $K_2Cr_2O_7$, and should require 0.25 ml of M/1 organic acid, if during oxidation a single molecule were to consume three atoms of oxygen. Using M/2 mandelic acid in the burette, a titre of 1.05 ml of acid would mean that one molecule consumes one atom of oxygen (reaction 1 or 2) and 0.75 ml acid will correspond to 2 atoms of oxygen (reaction 3). This was the concentration of mandelic acid always used. A stock of 0.15M manganous sulphate was also maintained for adjusting Mn(II) concentrations, where required. In some cases the solid salt had to be used. In mixtures, rich in sulphuric acid, a cherry-red colour developed on addition of $MnSO_4$, showing that it was oxidised to Mn(III) state by the dichromate, and the Mn^{3+} ion then perhaps oxidised the organic acid. The mixture lost this colour as the end point was approached. At the end point, the cherry-red colour turned to bluish green due to Cr(III). In general, the time required for equilibrium shortened as the concentrations of H_2SO_4 and $MnSO_4$ increased.

Over eighty titrations were carried out in which initial concentrations of H_2SO_4 and $MnSO_4$ were changed. The results are summarised in Table I. One inflection only is observed in most of the titration graphs, which is usually a steep one.

DISCUSSION

It will be observed that in these experiments we are following the *reduction* of dichromate rather than the oxidation of the organic acid. Some titration graphs, e.g., those corresponding to serial No. 25, 27, 30, 39, and 48, show a clear one-step reduction of dichromate, whereas in some others there is the possibility of an inflection corresponding to loss of oxygen not exceeding one-sixth of the total oxygen lost at the end of titration (No. 2, 13, 18, 61). Possibility of partial reduction of Cr(VI) to Cr(V) is implied:

Consumption of oxygen atoms per mole of mandelic acid is summarised in Table II. We have assumed that the final state of oxidation of chromium in these experiments is always Cr(III).

TABLE I

*Reduction of dichromate by mandelic acid.*Available oxygen present in the cell = 1.50 ml of *N*/1 solution.

Sl. No.	MnSO ₄ .	<i>M</i> /2-Mandelic acid added.	O atom per mole acid.	Sl. No.	MnSO ₄ .	<i>M</i> /2-Mandelic acid added.	O atom per mole acid.
A. H ₂ SO ₄ = 14 <i>N</i> .				B. H ₂ SO ₄ = 12 <i>N</i> .			
1	0.0000 <i>M</i>	0.75 ml	2.00	16	0.000 <i>M</i>	0.75	2.00
2	0.0025	0.75	2.00	17	0.0025	0.75	2.00
3	0.010	0.75	2.00	18	0.010	0.75	2.00
4	0.015	0.75	2.00	19	0.015	0.75	2.00
5	0.020	0.85	1.77	20	0.020	0.85	1.77
6	0.025	0.95	1.58	21	0.025	0.85	1.77
7	0.045	1.15	1.30	22	0.075	1.05	1.40
8	0.075	1.25	1.20	23	0.100	1.10	1.36
9	0.100	1.25	1.20	24	0.180	1.15	1.30
10	0.130	1.425	1.05	25	0.300	1.40	1.07
11	0.150	1.425	1.005	26	0.400	1.50	1.00
12	0.160	1.50	1.00	27	0.450	1.50	1.00
13	0.170	1.50	1.00	28	Saturated	1.50	1.00
14	0.300	1.50	1.00	..	..	..	..
15	Saturated	1.50	1.00	..	..	..	..
C. H ₂ SO ₄ = 10 <i>N</i> .				D. H ₂ SO ₄ = 8 <i>N</i> .			
29	0.0000 <i>M</i>	0.75	2.00	41	0.0000 <i>M</i>	1.15	1.30
30	0.0025	0.75	2.00	42	0.0005	0.95	1.58
31	0.0050	0.85	1.77	43	0.005	1.15	1.30
32	0.0100	0.85	1.77	44	0.040	1.15	1.30
33	0.020	0.85	1.77	45	0.175	1.15	1.30
34	0.035	0.85	1.77	46	0.300	1.35	1.11
35	0.050	0.85	1.77	47	0.400	1.35	1.11
36	0.075	0.95	1.58	48	0.500	1.50	1.00
37	0.400	1.45	1.04	49	0.600	1.50	1.00
38	0.450	1.50	1.00	50	Saturated	1.50	1.00
39	0.500	1.50	1.00	..	..	..	..
40	Saturated	1.50	1.00	..	..	..	..
E. H ₂ SO ₄ = 6 <i>N</i> .				F. H ₂ SO ₄ = 4 <i>N</i> .			
51	0.000 <i>M</i>	1.20	1.25	58	0.00 <i>M</i>	1.35	1.11
52	0.035	1.35	1.11	59	0.01	1.30	1.15
53	0.400	1.35	1.11	60	0.40	1.35	1.11
54	0.500	1.35	1.11	61	0.55	1.40	1.07
55	0.550	1.40	1.07	62	0.60	1.50	1.00
56	0.600	1.50	1.00	63	Saturated	1.50	1.00
57	Saturated	1.50	1.00				

Table II shows that a mixture, rich in sulphuric acid, induces a consumption of two atoms of oxygen. This oxidation is not observed below 10*N*-H₂SO₄. Only a small amount of MnSO₄ has to be introduced into the mixture to suppress this reaction. On the other hand, when enough MnSO₄ has been added, each mixture may lead to consumption of one atom oxygen only. For two atoms of oxygen consumed, there is only one reaction possible, viz., reaction (3). For one atom of O, there are two possibilities, viz., (1) or (2). We isolated both benzoic acid and benzoylformic acid from these mixtures by the usual

method, recrystallised, and checked their melting points. Benzaldehyde was not found. The dichromate present was enough to oxidise 1.5 ml of $N/1$ - $MnSO_4$ to $Mn(III)$. Under standard conditions the chances for oxidation of $Mn(II)$ to $Mn(III)$ by dichromate are not bright as the E° values for Mn^{3+}/Mn^{2+} and $Cr_2O_7^{2-}/Cr^{3+}$ will show (+1.51 and +1.33 respectively), but in our mixtures these values may be altered. The cherry-red colour of many mixtures does show the conversion to $Mn(III)$ and the final bluish green colour, a reduction of $Cr(VI)$ to $Cr(III)$. Table II shows that both reactions (1) and (3) can take place without $Mn(II)$ in the system. It can only accelerate the reactions concerned.

TABLE II

Summary of neat ratios.

$M/2$ Mandelic acid in the burette. Dichromate = 50 ml of $0.005M = 0.25$ ml of $M/1$ in cell; 0.25 ml of $M/1$ - $K_2Cr_2O_7$ requires $0.25 \times 3 \times 2$ ml or 1.50 ml of $M/1$ acid if one molecule takes one atom O.

H_2SO_4 .	$MnSO_4$.	O atom/mole acid.	H_2SO_4 .	$MnSO_4$.	O atom/mole acid.
14N	0—0.015	2	8N	0—	(1.3)
	0.18—sat.	1		0.5—sat.	1
12N	0—0.015	2	6N	0—	(1.25)
	0.4—sat.	1		0.6—sat.	1
10N	0—0.0025	2	4N	0—	(1.11)
	0.45—sat.	1		0.6—sat.	1
			2N— $N/4$	0—sat.	1

Table I shows that the oxygen requirement per mole of mandelic acid is in most cases between 1 and 2. We are therefore inclined to consider that both benzoic and benzoylformic acids are simultaneously produced. It is not impossible that the same equilibrium constant may cover both the products. The size of the inflection is related to the equilibrium constant and if there is only one constant concerned, we need not look for another inflection. Two equilibrium constants of comparable magnitude, perhaps related to reactions (1) and (3), will produce the same results. The main point of interest in these titrations then becomes the situation that an increase in Mn^{2+} concentration may completely suppress reaction (3) though all the other conditions, including (H^+) , are the same. It seems that Mn^{2+} accelerates reaction (1) much more than (3) does; perhaps it may decelerate the latter.

We have therefore two conflicting choices before us: (i) to regard the production of benzoylformic acid and benzoic acid as an integrated process involving only one equilibrium constant; (ii) to regard the production of the two acids as independent, involving two independent reactions and equilibrium constants, the rate of one of which (benzoylformic acid) is greatly accelerated by introduction of Mn^{2+} ions. It is cogent that the oxidation of benzoylformic acid by dichromate should be separately studied before a proper choice can be made. We also feel that the initial concentration of dichromate should be increased to see whether new results are obtained and a fresh attempt to carry out these titrations in the reverse should be made.

As already mentioned (*vide supra*), the oxidation with acid dichromate is in line with those with dilute nitric acid and acid permanganate in so far as reactions (1) and (3) are observed to the exclusion of (2). On the other hand, when the oxidising

agents are lead tetra-acetate, SeO_2 , V (v) in perchloric or sulphuric acid, manganic pyrophosphate or Ce (iv) in sulphuric acid, reactions (2) and (3) are observed. We have previously described analogous results in acid dichromate oxidation of lactic acid. Recently, Mishra and Symons⁹ have thrown some light on the nature of oxy-anions of transition metals in sulphuric acid or oleum. They are inclined to the view that substances like $\text{O}_2\text{Mn}(\text{OSO}_3\text{H})_3$ or $\text{O}_2\text{Cr}(\text{OS}_2\text{O}_6\text{H})_2$ may be formed, instability of which is considerable, depending on the varying degrees of electron affinity of the ligands, leading even to oxygen extrusion. This shows that due care is necessary in using E° data for predicting results in an actual reaction and specific effects may be expected here and there. How far one-electron and many-electron transfers are responsible for the differences, noted here, also deserves consideration.

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